

RESEARCH ARTICLE | OPEN ACCESS**Effect of Motivation on Organizational Growth of Enugu State Ministry of Housing****Ozougwu, Leticia Chima¹, Prof Ejike Okonkwo², & Nnadi, Chikezie Sunday Onoh PhD³**¹²³*Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu****Corresponding Author****Background**

Growth in organisations is directed to the performance of motivated employees. Motivated employees direct their efforts towards achieving organizational goals and positive returns. They get satisfaction from reaching their goals and finding value in their job. Motivation is a particular tool, factor that inspires people to work both individually and as a group to produce the best results for business in the most efficient manner. It is a thing that makes something to happen, this has become the major reason why so many organizations grow into multinational status and also give out more profit margin than expected (Elite, 2022). without motivation as a catalyst to inspire or motivate a group of people who work under or for an organization, it would be very difficult to make a relative profit margin, because the workers who now have difficult unions which they rally around for job security and welfare have come to capitalize on motivations as a factor to greater workers productivity. A motive initiates an action or certain behaviour for the fulfilment of a

specific goal, and this directly corresponds to the desire of an individual. Motivators are the tools used for motivating employees, such as promotions and pay bonuses. The act of motivation is the actual process of completing a task and this usually depends on the motives and motivators (LSBF, 2020; Ukwuani, Mbah & Ugochukwu, 2018).

Organizations cannot exist without growth. Growth is something for which most companies, large or small, strive. It has the potential to provide organisations with a variety of benefits, including greater ability to withstand market fluctuations, increased power and greater efficiencies from economies of scale. Understanding the key stages of organizational growth can be essential to ensuring the longevity of the organisation. Indeed, (2022) asserts that organizational growth is a stage a company reaches when it can consider expansion and may look for additional options to generate more revenue. Organizational growth is often a function of industry growth trends, business lifecycle and the owners' desire for equity value creation. Organizational growth may work contrary to the interests of some, or even most, members of the organization. Establishing and improving standard practices is often a key

ABSTRACT

The study evaluated effect of motivation on organizational growth of Enugu State Ministry of Housing. The specific objectives were to; examine the effect of increase in salary on the output and evaluate the effect of career development on the reduced expenses of Enugu State ministry of housing. The descriptive survey design was used. A total population of 272 staff was used. The whole population was used due to small number A total of 263 staff returned the questionnaire accurately filled, which gave 97 percent response rate. Data were presented and analysed using mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Z – test. The findings indicated that the Salary had significant positive effect on the output $Z(95, n = 263), 5.981 < 8.710 = p. < 0.05$ and Career development had significant positive effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing $Z(95, n = 263), 7.723 < 9.450 = p. < 0.05$. The study concluded that salary and career development had significant positive effect on the output and reduced expenses of Enugu State ministry of housing. The study recommended among others that it is not a must that organization salary structure should be based on the labour union salary structure because most times these employees perform task, duties and services that are far more hectic compared to their salary.

Keywords: Motivation; Organisational Growth; Enugu State Ministry of Housing

Citation: Ozougwu, L. C., Okonkwo, E. & Nnadi, C. S. O. (2024). Effect of Motivation on Organizational Growth of Enugu State Ministry of Housing. *European Journal of Finance and Management Sciences* 8(1), 1-15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10723962>

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element of organizational growth as well. Indeed, a small business that undergoes a significant burst of growth will find its operations transformed in any number of ways. And often, it will be the owner's advance planning and management skills that will determine whether that growth is sustained, or whether internal constraints rein in that growth prematurely. Organizational growth is essentially a quantitative process through which the structure of a multiagent system organization increases the number of its roles and links (IGI, 2023).

Ministry of Housing is the government ministry, charged with the responsibility to plan, devise and implement the state policies on Housing. Alina & Armenia (2015) asserts that in time of globalisation and continuous change, public institutions face the challenges of satisfying population' requirements, having reduced resources at their disposal. In order to be able to provide qualitative public services to the citizens, public institutions need to focus on the only resource that can help an organisation flourish and successfully achieve their mission. However, building and maintaining a capable and competitive workforce has proved to be an important challenge for public organisations. Motivation is one of the major reasons people work, it drives people to succeed and reach their goals. This plays an important role in enhancing an organisation's development.

An employee's motivation can play a big part in organisational behaviour, as it is a fundamental part of how the employee performs in their role and how they assist the organisation in attaining their goals (IPM, 2023). The effective direction, motivation and leadership, takes a business forward. Amongst all, motivation plays the key role as it helps to identify and satisfy the needs of employees and the organisation. Managers use various motivational programmes to encourage employees to achieve their maximum potential leading to improved organisational performance. Motivation is the core of Management. A team of highly qualified and motivated employees is necessary for achieving the objectives of an organization. Motivation in the public service is an attribute of government and non-governmental organization (NGO) employment that explains why individuals have a desire to serve the public and link their personal actions with the overall public interest. It helps employees get the most out of their job experience and is rapidly evolving to work towards employee goals and organizational needs effectively (Gottfredson, 2015). Absence of good reward would bring about decline in performance, which will automatically affect the organizational growth. These necessitate the study on the effect of motivation on organizational growth: A study of Enugu State Ministry of Housing.

Statement of the Problem

Motivation, forces acting either on or within a person to initiate behaviour. Motivation of an individual is also influenced by the presence of other people. Motivation is crucial because it allows us to change behaviour, develop competencies, be creative, set goals, grow interests, make plans, develop talents, and boost engagement. With motivated employees, organizations can increase the quality and quantity of the work they produce. Higher motivation leads to job satisfaction in workers. Opportunities for need satisfaction make employees loyal and committed to the organization.

Motivation is imperative for an organisation's growth. An organization's progress is directly related to the motivated employees working in it. Motivated employees direct their efforts towards achieving organizational goals and positive returns. They get satisfaction from reaching their goals and finding value in their job. Nevertheless, most organizations often encounter problems during motivation as a result of poor salary increase and unimproved employee career development. Lack of clarity or alignment with the purpose, goals, or expectations of their work, a lack of feedback or recognition, a lack of autonomy or empowerment, a lack of challenge or variety, and a lack of support or resources.

Motivation being a key factor in improving employees performance and organizational growth. Without these elements, employees may feel confused, frustrated, ignored, undervalued, restricted, micromanaged, powerless, bored, complacent, overwhelmed, stressed, or burned out. Also, poor motivation in the organization often leads to meagre output and reduced expenses. This has necessitated for the study on the effect of motivation on organizational growth: A study of Enugu State Ministry of Housing.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of motivation on organizational growth of Enugu State Ministry of Housing. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the effect of increase in salary on the output of Enugu State ministry of housing
- ii. Evaluate the effect of career development on the reduced expenses of Enugu State ministry of housing

Research Question

- i. What is the effect of increase in salary on the output of Enugu State ministry of housing?
- ii. To what extent does career development effect reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing?

Test of Hypothesis

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Increase in salary has effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing
- ii. Career development has effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing

Significance of the Study

Organization: The study is of great benefit to the organization as it will help them to identify the best methods to motivate their employees and as well adopt the best strategies for organizational growth. If all managers can motivate workers to their tasks, they can increase organizational performance.

Employee: The study is very significant to the employees as it will help them to be motivated to their satisfaction. It will also help them to realize that their been motivated in the organization is to improve their performance.

Researcher/Academia: The study is also not in doubt as it provides a good premise for future research. It also adds to existing literature on employee motivation and its effects on organization growth.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Motivation

Motivation involves needs and desires as such the key to motivation is the satisfaction of desires. Motivation is in essence what is considered to be what drive behaviour, action and importantly persistence. Motivation is the word derived from the word 'motive' which means needs, desires, wants or drives within the individuals. It is the process of stimulating people to actions to accomplish the goals (Juneja 2015). Motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behaviour at a given time. Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behaviour. Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behaviour. It is often held that different mental states compete with each other and that only the strongest state determines behaviour (*Wasserman and Wasserman, 2020*). Motivating employees, is an intrinsic and internal drive to put forth the necessary effort and action towards work-related activities. Motivation is defined as the "psychological forces that determine the direction of a person's level of effort and a person's level of persistence in the face of obstacles"

Components of Motivation Used in the Study

Salary

Salary is the periodic specific amount of money given to an employee at the end of the month. Salary is often commensurate to the job and duties of the employee. Ldama, & Nasiru, (2020) defined salary as the process of compensating an organisation's employees in accordance with accepted policy and procedures. An important component of a successful organizations' salary and wage administration policy is monitoring and evaluating all employee's compensation to ensure that they are being paid appropriately, both with respect to others in the same organization and to the marketplace as a whole. Surbhi (2015) and Mbah, Nwatu & Okwor (2021) also sees salary as a fixed amount paid to the employees at regular intervals for their performance and productivity whereas wages are the hourly- based payment given to the labour for the amount of work finished in a day. Salaries are typically determined by comparing market pay-rates for people performing similar work in similar industries in the same region. Salary is also determined by levelling the pay rates and salary ranges established by an individual employer. Salary is also affected by the number of people available to perform the specific job in the employer's employment locale (Susan, 2016).

Career Development

Career development is a continuous process where both employees as well as employers have to put efforts in order to create conducive environment so that they can achieve their objectives at the same time. Career Development Association of Alberta (2018) defined career development as "the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure, and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future". Career development is the proactive, lifelong process of finding your footing and advancing your career path. It's an intentional approach to creating a meaningful career that includes setting long-term goals, exploring professional development opportunities, and gaining new work experience. Professionals who develop their careers through an organization tend to have more resources available (Upwork, 2023 & Ugwu,2021). Career development involves self-knowledge, exploration, and decision-making that shapes career. It requires successfully navigating occupational options to choose and train for jobs that suit individual's personality, skills, and interests.

Organisation

Organisation refers to individuals who are gathered together with the aim of achieving a specific purpose. Organization refers to a collection of people, who are involved in pursuing defined objectives. Business, (2023) defined organization as a social system which comprises all formal human relationships. The organization encompasses division of work among employees and alignment of tasks towards the ultimate goal of the company. It can also be referred as the second most important managerial function that coordinates the work of employees, procures resources and combines the two, in pursuance of company's goals. Organization is a goal-oriented process, which aims at achieving them, through proper planning and coordination between activities. It relies on the principle of division of work and set up authority-responsibility relationship among the members of the organization. The organization structure is a basic idea, which depends on the activity authority relationship in the company. It is designed in such a way to realise business objectives (Business, 2023 & Ede, & Mbah, 2020).

Organizational Growth

Growth is a major concern for all businesses because it spurs prosperity and survival. Organizational growth, however, means different things to different organizations. The most meaningful yardstick is one that shows progress with respect to an organization's stated goals. Organizational growth is associated with organizational change; both of which affect employees' perception of organization support (Furxhi, Stillo & Teneqexhi, 2016). Although there are a variety of approaches used to measure organizational growth, it is essentially a dynamic measure of change over time. Starbuck, (1967) in the study of Walters (2020), defines organizational growth as "change in an organization's size when size is measured by the organization's membership or employment". Also, organizational growth is primarily conceptualized as employee growth. Organizational growth is often a function of industry growth trends, business lifecycle and the owners' desire for equity value creation.

Components of Organizational Growth

Output

Output in economics is the "quantity (or quality) of goods or services produced in a given period, by a firm, industry, or organization. It is the result of an organizational input to its activity or process. Output is a measure of all the goods and services produced in a given time period by businesses in that industry and sold either to consumers or to businesses outside that industry. Output can be consumed directly or sold to other businesses for use in producing other output. The output of the business enterprise is aimed at the fulfilment or satisfaction of human needs. Output is an assessment of the efficiency of a worker or group of workers in an organization. This is defined as the number of goods and services or waste products that are produced by an employee. Employee output shows the capacity of a company to efficiently or inefficiently achieve independent goals (Ede & Mbah, 2020). The term may refer to all the work, energy, goods, or services produced by an individual, company, factory or machine. In the world of computing, it refers to any data that has been processed by and sent out from a computer or similar electronic device.

Reduced Expenses

Expenses means those expenses incurred, either by the organization, on behalf of the organization or for which the organization has agreed to make reimbursement. An expense is the cost of operations that a company incurs to generate revenue. It is simply defined as the cost one is required to spend on obtaining something (Liberto, James, & Li, 2022). Reduced expenses are also known as cost reduction. *Cost reduction* set ambitious yet achievable targets that create healthy organizational tension. Cost reduction is the process of decreasing a company's expenses to maximize profits. It involves identifying and removing expenditures that do not provide added value to customers while also optimizing processes to improve efficiency. Cost reduction typically focuses on generating short-term savings (Gartner, 2023).

Conceptual Review

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher, 2023

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Expectancy Theory by Vroom in the year 1964

Expectancy Theory

Vroom's expectancy theory assumes that behaviour results from conscious choices among alternatives whose purpose it is to maximize pleasure and to minimize pain. Vroom realized that an employee's performance is based on individual factors such as personality, skills, knowledge, experience and abilities. Vroom's theory is based on the belief that employee effort will lead to performance and performance will lead to rewards (Vroom, 1964). Rewards may be either positive or negative. The more positive the reward the more likely the employee will be highly motivated. Vroom Expectancy theory proposes that an individual will behave or act in a certain way because they are motivated to select a specific behaviour over others due to what they expect the result of that selected behaviour will be. In essence, the motivation of the behaviour selection is determined by the desirability of the outcome (Oliver, 1974).

Empirical Review

The Effect of Salary on the Output

Okeke, Nwele and Achilike (2017) conducted a study on Impact of effective wages and salary administration on civil service productivity in Nigeria: A Study of Anambra State. The objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between wages administration and employee performance in the civil service; and to examine the constraints to full implementation of minimum wage by state governments in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design, an item structured instrument developed to reflect the modified 5 points Likert Scale format was used to elicit information from the respondents. The population consisted of 2951 Civil Servants from which a sample of 557 respondents was selected, using a formula developed by Borg and Gall (1973). Whereas percentages and mean ratings were used to answer the research questions, Chi-square (χ^2) test of independence and T- test for independent large sample, ($n > 30$) were used to test the hypotheses. The study revealed that employees need effective salary and wages administration to achieve high productivity in the civil service. The study found also that poor leadership and lack of political will were the major reasons for not fully implementing the minimum wage policy by some state governments including Anambra State.

Eneh, Nwekpa and Udu (2018) carried out a study on Salary Increase and Employee Productivity in Cement Manufacturing Companies in South-South, Nigeria. The study examined the extent to which salary increase as independent variable (x) influences employee productivity in cement manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. A study adopted survey design. A sample size of 310 was determined from a population of 1,381 staff, using Taro Yamane sample size determination formula. The questionnaires collated were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings revealed that salary increase has significant relationship with employee productivity in cement manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. The findings show that employees are motivated by monetary rewards and they are induced to expend greater effort in a task if those efforts are rewarded directly through performance-related pay. The study concluded that employee salary should be determined and increase based on productivity of the employee as this will help to create competition among the employees to attain the set goals of the firm.

Ileka, & Muogbo (2020) on wages and salary administration and employee performance in selected Government ministries in Anambra State. This study investigated wages and salary administration and employee performance in selected government ministries in Anambra State. Specifically, the study examined how wages and salaries, cash bonus, minimum wage, fringe benefits and monetization of fringe benefit affect employee performance. Relevant theoretical, conceptual and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on Maslow's Hierarchy of needs. Survey research design was employed and a total of nine government ministries were studied. The population of the study constituted 1920 employees of the selected government ministries out of which 374 employees were sampled for the study. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument for data collection. Simple percentage analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis were employed in analysing the data. The study found that wages and salaries have significant positive effect on employee performance; cash bonus has significant positive effect on employee performance; minimum wage has significant negative effect on employee performance; fringe benefits have significant positive effect on employee performance; and monetization of fringe benefits has significant positive effect on employee performance in selected government ministries in Anambra state. The study concluded that effective wages and salary administration have significant positive effective on civil service performance. The study recommended that government should give priority to the welfare of those in its employment because they can make or mar government programmes.

Akpa et al. (2020) conducted a study on Knowledge Management and Performance of Organizations: A Case Study of Selected Food and Beverage Firms. The objective of this paper is to ascertain the effect of knowledge management on the performance of organizations in Nigerian food and beverage manufacturing sector. To achieve the stated objective, the study used survey research design, with 320 samples from a population of 1587 employees of selected food and beverage firms in Nigeria. A validated questionnaire was used to collect data and structural equation modelling was used to analyse the data. Results showed that knowledge creation had a significant negative effect on innovation and knowledge sharing had a significant positive effect on innovation. The findings also revealed that knowledge creation has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction while knowledge sharing had an insignificant negative effect on job satisfaction. Practical Implication: The results can be used in efforts to improve the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria and other developing countries by adopting knowledge management initiatives to enhance performance levels.

Eke, Anagha, and Dickson (2021) carried out a study on the Effect of Capital Allowance on Manufacturing Companies in Enugu State Nigeria. This study examined the effect of capital allowance on manufacturing companies in Enugu state Nigeria. The study adopted the Survey research design while the primary source of data was the source of data engaged for the purpose of this study. Forty-five Staff members from three accounting units of three manufacturing companies in Enugu state Nigeria were administered copies of the questionnaire. The study tested the research hypotheses with Z test statistical tool with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Findings from this study revealed that Annual allowance have significant effect on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Enugu state. The study also revealed that initial allowance does not have significant effect on the efficiency of manufacturing companies in Enugu state.

The Effect of Career Development on the Reduced Expenses

Osibajo, Oyewunmi & Ibinyinka (2015) evaluated the career development as a determinant of Organizational Growth: Modelling the Relationship between these Constructs in the Nigerian Banking Industry. Career development is argue to be " an ongoing, formalized effort " engage by organizations in enriching the organization's human resources in alignment with employees' and the organization's needs. A sample was drawn from First City Monument Bank (FCMB) with two hundred and sixty five respondents. SPSS was used to analyse demographic characteristics of the respondents, while AMOS 21 was adopted for the Structural Equation modelling of the survey model. Many of the associations between the tested variables were strong and positive. However, all the tested independent variables such as reward, recognition, skills, promotion had positive impact on organizational growth, while experience had negative impact. Results support the literature, in terms of the relationships between independent and dependent variables with the exception of experience, which had negative impact on organizational growth. Therefore, management should employ better strategies in retaining their experienced employees, which tends to effect on the organizational growth.

Babatunde (2017) examined the effect of cost control and cost reduction Techniques in Organizational Performance. In any organization, the major objective is to maximize profit, but the main constraints facing them are the rise in cost of operation. Due to this, the cost of production increases and could lead to certain cost control and cost reduction which make it complex for many organizations to operate as well organised cost limit of knowledge. The study aims to critically examine and evaluate the application of cost control and cost reduction in organizational performance and also to review the budget as an effective tool of cost control and cost reduction. A descriptive survey research was adopted. A total number of 50 questionnaires were administered and used for the study. The analysis of data collected was undertaken by applying appropriate statistical tools. Regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis with the use of SPSS. Based on the findings, it was evident that cost control has a positive impact on organizational performance and also the style of management has a positive impact on organizational performance

Egbide, et al., (2019) conducted a study on cost reduction strategies and the growth of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The problem of high manufacturing costs has led to the shutdown of many manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This study examines the relationship between cost reduction strategies and the growth of manufacturing companies in Nigeria using data from annual reports of 40 manufacturing companies quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange within the period of 2012-2016. 40 manufacturing companies were sampled purposively for this study. The study took changes in material cost, changes in labour cost and changes in administrative overhead as variables for cost reduction strategies while changes in turnover as the variable for Growth. Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the association cost reduction strategies and growth while, regression analysis was used to determine the impact of cost reduction strategies on the growth of manufacturing companies. Results showed a positive significant relationship between cost reduction strategies and growth of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study recommends that manufacturing companies should implement value analysis in order to reduce material costs and the implementation of cost reduction strategies in all manufacturing companies in Nigeria

Nwatu and Idoko (2020) Reducing operating costs and profitability of manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The study evaluates the reducing operating costs and profitability of manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: Examine the relationship between bank charges and the growth of manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria. Evaluate the relationship between travelling expenses and the value per unit products of manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria. Investigate the relationship between selling costs and income of the manufacturing firms in south East, Nigeria. The study used the survey approach. The primary sources were personal interview and the administration of questionnaire. A population of 3866 staff was used. The population of the study

was drawn from the groups under study using a stratified sampling method. The adequate sample size of 350, using Freund and William's statistic formula was applied. 328 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 94 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.84 which was also good. Data was presented and analysed by mean score (3.0 and above a greed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool. The findings of the study reveal that Bank Charges and the growth of manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria are significantly related of manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria. $r(94, n=328)=0.639, p>.05$. Travelling expenses and the value per unit product of manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria are significantly related $r(94, n=328) = .0.528, p>.05$. Selling costs and income of the manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria is significantly related $r(94, n=328)=0.598, P>.0$.

Mbah & Maduafor (2022) conducted a study on Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study examines the effect of knowledge management and organizational performance of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. Three research question and hypotheses guide the study. Relevant conceptual theoretical and empirical literature was reviewed. The study was anchored on knowledge-based view (KBV). The study adopted survey research design. This study was carried out in Enugu State, Nigeria. Therefore, the population of the study comprised 1590. The sample size consisted 310 was obtained using statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall. This study made use of primary source of data. The research instrument was questionnaire, which was subjected to face and content validity procedures. Data gathered was retested using Cronbach Alpha. The data collected were analysed using simple percentages to answer the research questions while multiple regression was used in test the hypotheses. The result shows that knowledge accessibility has a significant positive influence on market share in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms; Knowledge sharing has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms and Knowledge creation has a significant positive influence on employee efficiency in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study concluded that knowledge management had a significant positive effect on organization performance using pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Summary of Reviewed Empirical Related Literature

Most of the studies reviewed were not specifically centred on the topic of the present study effect of motivation on organizational growth: A study of Enugu State Ministry of Housing. Most of these were on Impact of effective wages and salary administration on civil service productivity in Nigeria: A Study of Anambra State, Salary Increase and Employee Productivity in Cement Manufacturing Companies in South-South, Nigeria, Wages and Salary Administration And Employee Performance In Selected Government Ministries In Anambra State, Knowledge Management and Performance of Organizations: A Case Study of Selected Food and Beverage Firms, effect of cost control and cost reduction Techniques in Organizational Performance, cost reduction strategies and the growth of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Reducing operating costs and profitability of manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria etc. This study reviewed were analysed using Chi-square, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, Simple percentage analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis, and structural equation modelling. Another gap was also in the area of currency and geographical location. Hence, the need to fill these observed gaps.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey design. The survey research is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analysing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The survey design was adopted because the study requires a technique of observation such as questionnaire and or interview, the population of the study must be carefully chosen, clearly defined and specifically delimited and roles upon observation for the acquisition of data and it is more economical.

Source of Data

Data are classified as either primary or secondary data. The classification was based on the two possible sources: primary source and secondary source.

Primary Source

The primary source was questionnaire. A primary data source is the one which the data is collected directly (usually first-hand) by the researcher and so, the staff of Enugu state ministry of Housing was used.

Sources of Secondary Data

Secondary data source is the one which the data is obtained from published materials, internet websites, reports, dailies, text books and so on from the library of the institutions understudy. Sources of secondary can be split into two parts internal and external sources.

Area of Study

The area of the study was Enugu state ministry of Housing, Enugu state, Nigeria. *Kingsway Rd, G.R.A., Enugu, Nigeria*

Population of the Study

The population of the study was two hundred and seventy-two (272) staff of the Ministry of housing, Enugu state.

Sample Size Determination

The whole population was used due to small number.

Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling with a random start was adopted so as to give every unit of the population under study equal opportunity of being selected into sample. The secondary data were collected from firms, journals, publication, textbooks and the internet. Ten questions (10) in the questionnaire were ranged.

Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the staff. Ten (10) designed questionnaire was used. The responses generated were used thereafter for data analyses.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

This was done by administering 20 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study. Cronbah’s Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability. A Cronbach’s alpha value (∞) of greater 0.810 indicated very strong reliability.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach’s Alpha	No. of Items
.87	10

Scale reliabilities were calculated using Cronbach’s Alpha; the result obtained was 0.810. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale is good for the purpose of this study because it is greater than 0.87 which was good.

Method of Data Analyses

Data from the questionnaire were analysed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages and correlation co-efficient. Data from the questionnaire were further analysed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analysing the findings.

Scale: Strongly Agree (SA) -5, Agree (A) - 4, Neutral(N) -3, Disagree (D) -2, Strongly Disagree (SD),1

Decision Rule: If mean ≥ 3.0 , the respondents agree and If mean ≤ 3.0 , the respondents disagree. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis and Z - test was used to test the hypotheses and analysed with the aid of SPSS.

Results

The Effect of Salary on the Output of Enugu State Ministry of Housing

Table 2: Responses on the effect of salary on the output of Enugu State ministry of housing

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	The individual income influences the output to be generated.	615 123 46.8	148 37 14.1	168 56 21.3	52 26 9.9	21 21 8.0	1004 263 100%	3.82	1.330	Agree
2	The salary of the employees determines the services.	585 117 44.5	148 37 14.1	189 63 24.0	54 27 10.3	19 19 7.2	995 263 100%	3.78	1.306	Agree
3	Properly compensating employees feel valued and better coming to work.	485 97 36.9	148 37 14.1	243 81 30.8	48 24 9.1	24 24 9.1	948 263 100%	3.60	1.309	Agree
4	Fair compensation lead to greater job satisfaction.	545 109 41.4	228 57 21.7	171 57 21.7	34 17 6.5	23 23 8.7	1001 263 100%	3.81	1.283	Agree
5	Lower employee turnover as a result of good salary.	655 131 49.8	304 76 28.9	72 24 9.1	36 18 6.8	14 14 5.3	1081 263 100%	4.11	1.155	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.824	1.277	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 160 respondents out of 263 representing 60.9 percent agreed that the individual income influences the output to be generated with mean score 3.82 and standard deviation of 1.330. The salary of the employees determines the services 154 respondents representing 58.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation of 1.306. Properly compensating employees feel valued and better coming to work 134 respondents representing 51.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.60 and standard deviation of 1.309. Fair compensation lead to greater job satisfaction 166 respondents representing 63.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.81 and 1.283. Lower employee turnover as a result of good salary 207 respondents representing 78.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.11 and standard deviation 1.155.

Does Career Development Effect Reduced Expenses of Enugu State Ministry of Housing

Table 3: Responses on career development effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Skilled employees reduce waste.	505	360	60	74	15	1014	3.86	1.233	Agree
		101	90	20	37	15	263			
		38.4	34.2	7.6	14.1	5.7	100%			
2	Acquisition of knowledges promotes efficiency and effectiveness.	635	252	42	24	52	1005	3.98	1.231	Agree
		110	98	21	8	26	263			
		41.8	37.3	8.0	3.0	9.9	100%			
3	The employee morale is improved and man promotional vacancies internally.	680	332	60	12	18	1102	4.19	1.127	Agree
		136	83	20	6	18	263			
		51.7	31.6	7.6	2.3	6.8	100%			
4	The cost of managerial recruitment is reduced.	605	380	45	54	14	1098	4.11	1.124	Agree
		121	95	15	18	14	263			
		46.0	36.1	5.7	6.8	5.3	100%			
5	Career development ensues better utilization of employees skills.	420	460	45	64	17	1006	3.83	1.192	Agree
		84	115	15	32	17	263			
		31.9	43.7	5.7	12.2	6.5	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.994	1.181	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3, 191 respondents out of 263 representing 76.6 percent agreed that Skilled employees reduce waste with mean score 3.86 and standard deviation of 1.233. Acquisition of knowledges promotes efficiency and effectiveness 208 respondents representing 79.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.321. The employee morale is improved and man promotional vacancies internally 219 respondents representing 83.3 percent agreed with mean score of 4.19 and standard deviation of 1.127. The cost of managerial recruitment is reduced 216 respondents representing 82.1 percent agreed with mean score of 4.11 and 1.124. Career development ensues better utilization of employees' skills 199 respondents representing 75.6 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation 1.192.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses one: Increase in salary has effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing

Table 4: Z-test on increase in salary has effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing

		The individual income influences the output to be generated.	The salary of the employees determines the services.	Properly compensating employees feel valued and better coming to work.	Fair compensation lead to greater job satisfaction.	Lower employee turnover as a result of good salary.
N		263	263	263	263	263
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.468	.445	.369	.414	.537
	Positive	.080	.072	.091	.087	.053
	Negative	-.468	-.445	-.369	-.414	-.537
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.585	7.215	5.981	6.721	8.710
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Decision

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $5.981 < 8.710$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that increase in salary had significant positive effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.981 < 8.710$ against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that increase in salary had significant positive effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing.

Hypotheses Two: Career development has effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing

Table 5: Z-test on career development has effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing

		Skilled employees reduce waste.	Acquisition of knowledges promotes efficiency and effectiveness.	The employee morale is improved and man promotional vacancies internally.	The cost of managerial recruitment is reduced.	Career development ensues better utilization of employees skills.
N		263	263	263	263	263
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.476	.541	.583	.571	.507
	Positive	.057	.099	.068	.053	.065
	Negative	-.476	-.541	-.583	-.571	-.507
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.723	8.772	9.450	9.265	8.217
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Decision

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $7.723 < 9.450$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that career development had significant positive effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing.

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.723 < 9.450$ against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that career development had significant positive effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing

Discussions of Findings

Increase in Salary had Significant Positive Effect on the Output

Hypotheses one showed that comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.981 < 8.710$ against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that increase in salary had significant positive effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing. Eneh, Nwekpa and Udu (2018) carried out a study on Salary Increase and Employee Productivity in Cement Manufacturing Companies in South-South, Nigeria. The study examined the extent to which salary increase as independent variable (x) influences employee productivity in cement manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. Findings revealed that salary increase has significant relationship with employee productivity in cement manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. The findings show that employees are motivated by monetary rewards and they are induced to expend greater effort in a task if those efforts are rewarded directly through performance-related pay.

Career Development had Significant Positive Effect on Reduced Expenses

The problem of high manufacturing costs has led to the shutdown of many manufacturing companies in Nigeria. In the study of Egide, Adegbola, Bamidele, Sunday, Olufemi, & Eshua, (2019) on cost reduction strategies and the growth of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This study examined the relationship between cost reduction strategies and the growth of manufacturing companies in Nigeria using data from annual reports of 40 manufacturing companies quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange within the period of 2012-2016. 40 manufacturing companies were sampled purposively for this study. The study took changes in material cost, changes in labour cost and changes in administrative overhead as variables for cost reduction strategies while changes in turnover as the variable for Growth. Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the association cost reduction strategies and growth while, regression analysis was used to determine the impact of cost reduction strategies on the growth of manufacturing companies. Results showed a positive significant relationship between cost reduction strategies and growth of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. In line with this review hypothesis two showed that comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.723 < 9.450$ against the critical Z- value of $.000$ (2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that career development had significant positive effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were established by the study

- i. Salary had significant positive effect on the output of Enugu state ministry of housing $Z(95, n = 263), 5.981 < 8.710 = p. < 0.05$
- ii. Career development had significant positive effect on reduced expenses of Enugu state ministry of housing $Z(95, n = 263), 7.723 < 9.450 = p. < 0.05$

Conclusion

The study concluded that salary and career development had significant positive effect on the output and reduced expenses of Enugu State ministry of housing. This shows that when employees' salary is incommensurate to the level of work they perform in the organization, they would carry out their duties excellently. Also, career development helps employees to develop their potentials and as well live their lives in as much as they are living the life of the organization. Understanding the key stages of organizational growth can be essential to ensuring the longevity of the organisation because organizations cannot exist without growth.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the study

- i. It is not a must that organization salary structure should be based on the labour union salary structure because most times these employees perform task, duties and services that are far more hectic compared to their salary. Therefore managers/ organisations human resources department should ensure that employees are not given peanut as salary while they work as elephant.
- ii. There is a saying that thus declares that "we rise by lifting other" this is applicable to organizations that value the rise of their employees by creating avenues for their growth and development. This helps employees to feel belonged and as well strive to contribute their initiative in the achievement of organizational goal.

Contribution to Knowledge

The studies done were carried outside effect of motivation on organizational growth: A study of Enugu State Ministry of Housing and did not focus to best of my knowledge on salary and the output; and career development on the reduced expenses of Enugu State ministry of housing. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap

by evaluating the effect of motivation on organizational growth: A study of Enugu State Ministry of Housing. This model added to the contribution to knowledge.

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